

8-Acetyl-7-Hydroxy-4-Methyl Coumarin as a Gravimetric Reagent for Cu^{+2} and Fe^{+3}

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Manuscript received 16 July 1974; revised 21 April 1975; accepted 5 June 1975

8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl coumarin has been found to be a chelating agent for Cu(II) and Fe(III) . It gives a leaf green precipitate of $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4)_2]$ at pH 4.8–5.5 and brown precipitate of $[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4)_3]$ at pH 4.2–4.8. Both the metals were gravimetrically estimated with an average error about one percent. Electronic spectral, magnetic and i. r. spectral studies of the complexes were made.

SUBSTITUTED coumarins are better chelating agents,¹⁻⁵ with this view 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl coumarin (AHMC) has been prepared and its chelates with Cu(II) and Fe(III) have been estimated gravimetrically, when present in the different solutions. Electronic spectral, magnetic and i. r. spectral data have been found useful in establishing the stoichiometry of the chelates.

Experimental

Copper acetate, ferric acetate and sodium acetate (BDH or AR) were used and AHMC was prepared by the reported method^{6,7}, m. p. 160° (Found: C, 65.9; H, 4.42; $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 66.1; H, 4.58). The pH values were adjusted by adding suitable buffer solutions. All the pH measurements were carried out on Beckmann pH meter, magnetic measurements on Guoy's Balance and electronic spectral measurement were made on Bau-ch & Lomb spectronic '20'. The molecular weights of the chelates of Cu(II) and Fe(III) were determined cryoscopically.

Gravimetric Estimation of Fe^{+3} at Different pH values: Standard metal solution (10 ml) containing 8.5 mg of the metal is taken in 250 ml pyrex beaker. Varying quantities of different buffer solution were then added during the course of estimation to conclude about the suitable pH value. Thus from the gravimetric estimations it was concluded that the estimation was best carried out at pH 4.2–4.8. In the estimation one percent (1%) ethanolic solution of the reagent was added in excess with constant stirring. The metal complex is formed immediately. It is diluted to about 150 ml with distilled water and kept on boiling over a water bath with occasional stirring for 25 to 40 min. The digestion makes the precipitate granular. The complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4)_3]$ brown in colour is then filtered through a weighed sintered glass crucible No. 4. It is washed with ethanol (25%) till the washings are free of the reagent. It is dried to a constant weight by keeping it a 105° – 110° for 30 min. The results are recorded in Table 1.

The elemental analysis of the iron chelates is as follows: Found: C, 59.98; H, 3.75; Fe, 7.81; $\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4)_3$ requires: C, 61.10, H, 3.82; Fe, 7.92.

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF IRON AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES.

No.	pH	Fe^{+3} taken	Fe^{+3} complex	Fe^{+3} found	Error
1	3.6	0.0085	0.1013	0.0080	-.0005
2	4.2	0.0085	0.1025	0.0081	-.0004
3	4.6	0.0085	0.1064	0.0084	-.0001
4	4.8	0.0085	0.1085	0.0086	+.0001
5	5.0	0.0085	0.1057	0.0083	-.0002
6	6.5	0.0085	0.1025	0.0081	-.0004

Gravimetric Estimation of Copper: A known amount of cupric acetate solution was taken in a beaker and diluted to 150 ml with distilled water. The pH of the solution was adjusted in the range 4.8–5.5, the solution was heated on a water bath to about 60° and 1% ethanolic solution of reagent was gradually added with constant stirring. A leaf green precipitate of the copper complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4)_2]$ immediately separates out. The copper complex was digested on a water bath for about 30 min and then filtered in a weighed sintered glass crucible (G-4). The copper complex precipitate was washed several times with 30% ethanol. The precipitate was dried in an oven at 110° for about half an hour in order to get the constant weight.

The elemental analysis of the copper chelate is as follows:

Found: C, 57.72; H, 3.50; Cu, 12.76; $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4)_2$ requires: C, 57.84; H, 3.61; Cu, 12.85.

TABLE 2—ESTIMATION OF COPPER AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES.

No.	pH	Cu^{+2} taken	Cu^{+2} complex	Cu^{+2} found	Error
1	3.0	0.0332	0.2584	0.0325	-.0007
2	4.0	0.0332	0.2624	0.0330	-.0002
3	4.5	0.0332	0.2632	0.0331	-.0001
4	4.8	0.0332	0.2634	0.0333	+.0001
5	5.0	0.0332	0.2624	0.0330	-.0002
6	5.5	0.0332	0.2638	0.0332	Nil
7	6.0	0.0332	0.2557	0.0321	-.0011

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Effect of foreign Ions : Mn^{+2} , Co^{+2} , Cd^{+2} , Al^{+3} , Mg^{+2} , Ba^{+2} , Pb^{+2} , Tl^{+1} , Ni^{+2} , tartrate and oxalate interfere in these estimation while Zr^{+2} , Mo^{+6} and Zn^{+2} do not. The change in concentration of the reagent has no appreciable effect on the results. However, similar results were observed with other salts of the metals viz. $CuCl_2$, $CuBr_2$, $CuSO_4$, $FeCl_3$, $FeBr_3$ and $Fe_2(SO_4)_3$.

Spectral and Magnetic Studies : $Cu(II)$ forms 1:2 complex while $Fe(III)$ forms 1:3 complex. Composition of the complexes was confirmed by their elemental analysis, molecular weight and magnetic moment results. $Cu(II)$ having an electronic configuration d^9 should exhibit a magnetic moment higher than expected for one unpaired electron in tetrahedral complexes (1.75 – 2.21 B. M.). The magnetic moment value observed for $Cu(II)$ chelate is 1.81 B. M. which is consistent with tetrahedral symmetry. The spectrum of $Cu(II)$ chelate in DMF exhibits two absorption bands with peaks at $22,530\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $14,135\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The band at $22,530\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to intraligand charge transfer^{8,9} and band at $14,135\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to the transition ${}^3E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$. Therefore, it seems to possess tetrahedral configuration.

$Fe(III)$ having the electronic configuration $3d^5$ should exhibit magnetic moment (5.2-6.0 B. M.) in octahedral complexes. The observed value of magnetic moment 5.40, for iron chelate confirms octahedral symmetry. Further, confirmation of symmetry is made by electronic spectral bands. In the electronic absorption spectrum of iron chelate four bands are observed at $16,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $19,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $24,350\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $26,400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These bands are assigned to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$. The fourth band is assigned to ligand to metal charge transfer.

The splitting energy parameter Δ and interelectronic repulsion parameter B have been calculated as suggested

by Figgis¹⁰ and they appear to be $7,332\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 667 cm^{-1} respectively. The ratio $\frac{\Delta}{10B} = 1.1$, also favours high spin octahedral structure for the iron chelate.

Infrared Spectral Studies : In the i. r. spectrum of the ligand two important bands at 1680 cm^{-1} and 3560 cm^{-1} were observed due to $C=O$ and $-OH$ groups. In the i. r. spectra of the chelates of $Cu(II)$ and $Fe(III)$, these stretching frequencies are lowered, showing thereby complex formation through ketonic and hydroxyl groups. The observed stretching frequencies in $Cu(II)$ chelate are 1600 cm^{-1} and 3450 cm^{-1} and those in $Fe(III)$ chelate are 1610 cm^{-1} and 3470 cm^{-1} .

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. R. C. Saxena, Dr. R. P. Mahesh and Dr. S. K. Singhal for their suggestions. They are also thankful to Dr. O. P. Malik, research fellow in C.D.R.I. Lucknow for doing elemental analysis and i. r. spectra.

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